

The Journal of the Department of Religions
and Intercultural Studies, Faculty of Arts
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

LEAD CITY JOURNAL OF RELIGIONS AND INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

(ISSN 3043-4416)

Editorial Chief Consultant:
Anjola ROBBIN, PhD

Editor-in-Chief:
Ayodele Adeyinka ATOWOJU, PhD

Corresponding Editor:
Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD

Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication

(ISSN 3043-4416)

*The Journal of the Department of Religious and Intercultural
Studies, Faculty of Arts, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria*

Volume 2, Number 1, August 2024

Capacity Building and Administrative Skills Development Among Church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

Idowu Oladele OKUNLOLA

*Department of Religious Studies, Lead City University, Ibadan,
Nigeria*

idowuoladele75@gmail.com, +2348038602831

Ohuwaseun O. AFOLABI, PhD

*Department of Religious Studies, Lead City University, Ibadan,
Nigeria*

Abstract

Administrative skills that contribute to the effectiveness of church pastors in administering the church have witnessed a steady decline in recent times among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. Therefore, this study examined capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. The study employed a descriptive research design. Two sets of questionnaires were designed as instruments for pastors and church members. The sample was one hundred and sixty. Eighty church pastors and eighty church members responded respectively. Split-half method of calculating the reliability coefficient was used to check the reliability of the research instruments which yielded 0.786 and 0.740 respectively. Data collected were analysed using the SPSS package to get descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference give good attention to professional conferences like ministers' Conferences. The study also revealed that the extent of practicing administrative skills is high. The study disclosed that the prominent factor that affects capacity building is that some churches have policies that hinder their pastors from further training until after some years. Furthermore, capacity building improves the overall performance of pastors as a result of the administrative skills developed. Therefore, it can be concluded that capacity building leads to the development of administrative skills and this will bring

improvement to performance of the pastors. It is recommended that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should explore other opportunities like workshop, in-service training, to build their capacities and churches of Oyo Baptist Conference should make funds available to assist their pastors in capacity building.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Administrative Skills, Development, Oyo Baptist Conference, Church pastors

Introduction

Every organisation exists for specific purposes or objectives. Certain individuals must serve as administrators or managers to achieve the objectives. The church as an organisation exists for the work of mission, and to accomplish the church's purpose for existence, effective church administration is required (Ishola-Esan, 2014:33). In other words, any improvement and progress that is bound to happen to any organisation is a function of how that organisation is being administered (Ayandokun, 2016:8). This implies that to achieve the goal or purpose of the church excellent and effective church administration must be in place. There is an increase of knowledge in every area of life in the contemporary world, and that calls for a local church pastor to be competent and versatile in church administration (Fatiloro, 2018:1). Church administration that will be effective must not be devoid of administrative skills.

Church is the assembly of the redeemed persons, the called-out ones (West, 1963:3). These are the people who have experienced circumcision of the heart, having obtained salvation by grace through faith, and through forgiveness of their sins, and have decided to join the membership of a local church (though belonging to different denominations) (Akintola, 2020:193). From the perspective of another scholar, the church is seen as "the community of all true believers for all time" (Grudem, 1994:578). Church administration is the leadership that prepares the church to be the church and to do the work of the church. It is the guidance, and the usage of resources to move the church toward reaching its objectives (Tidwell, 1985:27). This definition points to the

considers it appropriate to investigate capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Statement of the Problem

Administrative skills that contribute to the effectiveness of church pastors in administering the church have witnessed a steady decline in recent times among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. This is reflected in the way some pastors are running activities of their churches. Furthermore, previous works around church administration have focused on diverse directions but none of these previous works have produced an empirical platform for the theoretical relationship between capacity building and administrative skills development among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference; hence, a gap to be filled. Therefore, the researcher examines capacity building and administrative skills development among pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This work sought to examine capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. The specific objectives were to: examine the nature of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference; find out the extent to which church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administration skills; identify factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference and investigate the benefits of capacity building to administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

Research Questions

This study attempted to provide answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the nature of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

2. To what extent does the church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administrative skills?
3. What are the factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?
4. What benefits does the capacity building have on administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Review of Literature

The Concept of Capacity Building

Every organisation that desires effectiveness and good results in particular areas must embark on developing the people that are working there. This cannot happen overnight, but it takes deliberate and conscious efforts to achieve this. Capacity building is an investment that most non-profit organisations like the church must invest in if they must produce good results after all profit-making organisations are doing well as far as this area is concerned. Yamoah (2014:139) affirms that human resources remain the greatest assets of any organisation, and as such, a considerable amount of resources must be voted for their development. Noort (2012:10), while quoting UNDP, opines that capacity building is the process “through which persons, organisations, and societies obtain, strengthen, and maintain the capacities to set and achieve their development objectives over time.” Odu, Ayodele, and Adebayo (2014:3) posit that capacity building is “all activities which can strengthen the knowledge, skills, abilities, and behaviours of an individual and improve institutional structures and process such that the organisation can proficiently sustainably meet its mission and goals.”

Again, Khan (2014:6), while citing Kuhl suggests that capacity building leads to building up new capacities. This relates to the position of Yamoah (2014:139) who insists that capacity building is “closely related to education, training and human resources development. Capacity building is a continuous process of adding values to individuals, organisations, and society so that they can be adequately prepared to

identify problems and formulate dynamic strategies to meet and solve the challenges.

Chatira and Mwenje (2018:110) and Andrews and Roller (2011) assert that the church is both a spiritual entity and an organization, and this implies that the pastor of a local church has the responsibility to lead both aspects of ministry (spiritual and organization). To do this, the pastor of a local church would need to develop more management and administrative skills because these skills will lead to effectiveness in ministry (Griffin, 2015:5 & Woodruff, 2004).

Pastoral periodic training is non-negotiable in building capacity among pastors of local churches. Chatira and Mwenje (2018:111) had earlier postulated that it is essential for pastors to improve themselves occasionally to keep up with the demands of ministry because a lot of damages have been caused by pastors who refused to upgrade or develop themselves. Furthermore, continuous learning by pastors of local churches to build their capacities especially in administrative skills line will help them to gain more knowledge, avoid limitation of scope, enhance their effectiveness, help them to relate with their parishioners on other aspects of life apart from spiritual matters, thus making them more relevant in ministry (Chatira & Mwenje, 2018:111).

Benefits of Capacity Building

There are a lot of benefits that follow every individual that takes a conscious effort to their capacity. Chatira and Mwenje (2018:111) claim that capacity building improves the effectiveness of pastors and making them more relevant in the ministry. Odu et al. (2014:3) also posit that capacity building strengthens the knowledge, skills, and abilities of individuals within an organisation. The position of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7) also corroborates with this statement when they argue that capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation and system improvement. Another benefit of capacity building through training is that it increases staff morale and motivation. Other benefits of capacity building include: Leaders become more relevant within the organisation (Graffin, 2015:5 & Woodruff, 2004); prevention of burn-

out (frustration) (Ojokuku & Adejare, 2014:7); expansion (growth) of the organisation; build competent individuals that is, beneficiary moves from one level of competence to a higher one (Biswas, 1996:401), to mention but few.

Nature of Capacity Building

Capacity building usually takes some nature/forms, which include In-service training, workshop/seminars, professional conferences, staff /workers meetings, refresher/further courses (Okenjom et al., 2017:477), and personal development through the reading of literature to mention but few.

In-Service Training- This is a mean for continuous professional growth. It is an integral part of the workers' development programme which is usually organised while in service (Nakpodia, 2011:290). Okenjom, et al. (2017:477) while reporting on the significance of in-service training to school administrators, also assert that in-service training provides a platform for regular updates of knowledge and competencies that are required for the implementation of school policies and curriculum. Osanwonyi (2016:83) believes that in-service training enhances job performance and the absence of it will retard professional growth. It is designed to fill the gap of professional inadequacies through regular participation.

Workshop/Seminar is another mean through which pastors can build their capacities. According to Ogbonaya (2011), a workshop/seminar serves as a training device for upgrading professional efficiency. It brings administrators together for the intent of learning new approaches to problem-solving in an organisation. The stance of Okenjom et al. (2017:477) corroborate that of Ogbonaya and claim that workshop/seminar makes administrators professionally more devoted to their work in the case of giving professional guidance to teachers in the various aspect of their specialisation for effective teaching and learning.

Staff/Workers Meetings- This is another on-the-job training platform that creates an opportunity for workers/staff to meet and discuss issues

achieved.” Planning could be short range or long range. In planning, likely problems to be encountered should be identified and discovered, and the probable solution highlighted (Ayandokun 2016:8-9; Murphey and Chand, 1973:136).

Organising

This skill has to do with deciding the pattern of relationships among persons who have a common task or purpose (Tidwell, 1985:207). Ishola-Esan (2014:32) also opines that it is a way of establishing effective interpersonal relationship that enables a particular organisation to work. That is, the arrangement of people to get the job done. It includes grouping related activities and setting up a line of authority (Wedel, 1966:33) at the same time putting the round pegs in the round holes for effectiveness (Ayandokun, 2016:9).

Directing

Directing is a skill that is important for effective administration. “It is of the order of instructing with authority. Directing is about indicating what others are to do” (Tidwell, 1985:210). In directing, followers are led to understand the minds of the leaders such as church pastor and to know what to do and how to do it. In this way, the followers will be able to contribute effectively. A good director is expected to indicate what others are to do in the group in a way that gets the job done and at the same time which reflects proper esteem for all persons (Tidwell, 1985:210-211).

Controlling

Everyone that will engage in leading the church needs a certain dose of controlling as an administrative skill. This skill has to do with directing, guiding, restraining, keeping with limits (Ogunbangbe, 2002:130). Control cannot operate without a defined objective that is embedded in planning. Hence, planning and controlling are the twin duties of a leader (pastor). One cannot be used successfully without the other. Planning is seen as the standard set to accomplish a set goal while controlling is the

measurement that is required to achieve the planned goal (Ogunbangbe, 2002:130).

Conceptual Framework

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Capacity Building

DEPENDENT VARIABLES

Administrative Skills Development

Figure 1: Conceptual Diagram for the Study

The diagram above shows the conceptual framework between capacity building which is the independent variable and administrative skills development which is the dependent variable. The parameters of the independent variable are the elements that stimulate capacity building. These parameters reflect the relationship between the strategies of capacity building to the development of administrative skills of the church pastors.

Theoretical Framework

This work, capacity building and administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference, is anchored on Human Capacity Theory (HCT). The centre idea of this theory is that people are great assets to any organization and any investment to improve their capacity will generate a meaningful return. Human Capacity Theory tries

to explain that formal education and training is remarkably essential in enhancing the productive and creative capacity of a population (Aladejebi, 2018:16). This theory also posits that an educated population is a productive and great asset to any nation and organization. Human capacity theorists assert that there is a positive relationship between formal education/training and productivity (Aladejebi, 2018:16).

Yamoah (2014:140) further explains that since there is a positive relationship between capacity building and productivity, thus, it is imperative to invest in human capital through education and training which can be obtained through diverse means such as workshops, In-service training, conferences, seminars, leaders and workers seminars, and personal development so that productivity gains can be made. Capacity building theorists also postulate that when people are subjected to education and training, it will impact on the workers' useful knowledge and skills, hence raising their productivity (Becker, 1964). Training and developing individuals within an organization is a mean of getting a better return from them (Nwankwo et al. 2015:20). Schuller (2000) also lends his voice to human capacity theory and states that skills, knowledge, and competence acquired through the capacity building will determine whether an organization or nation will prosper. Therefore, this theory suits this work because it emphasizes that an organization should focus on increasing the capacity of individuals or workers within that organization to increase their productivity or performance. In other words, if the pastor of a local church increases their capacity to acquire administrative skills through education and training, it will bring better performance to their pastoral ministry.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. The research instrument used for this study was questionnaire. Two questionnaires were designed for this study. The first questionnaire was designed for church pastors, while the second questionnaire was designed for church members. The questionnaires were developed by the researcher and partly adapted from the work of Okenjo *et al.* (2017:479) and Ojokuku

questionnaire was 94%. These questionnaires were sent to an analyst for data analysis. Responses gathered through the questionnaire were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to find percentage, mean scores, and standard deviation. Also, content analysis was also done for the open-ended question for proper interpretation.

Table 1: Shows Number of Sample Collected in Each Association

Association	Number of Pastor	Number of Church Member	of Total
Oyo North	10	10	20
Oyo South	10	10	20
Oyo West	10	10	20
Oyo East	10	10	20
AanuOluwwa	10	10	20
AyoOluwa	10	10	20
Bowen	10	10	20
Okediji	10	10	20
Total	80	80	160

Source: Field Work, 2024

Data Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: What are the natures of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Table 2: Nature of Capacity Building among Church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

S/N	Statements	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Capacity building entails adding values to already acquired competencies.	50	22	3		3.62	0.57	3 rd

2	It is enhanced through attending workshops.	34.7	60.0	4.0	1.3	3.28	0.6 1	8 th
3	Capacity building can be achieved through engaging in in-service training for pastors.	45.3	45.3	9.3		3.36	0.6 5	7 th
4	Attending professional conferences like ministers conference gives pastors opportunities to breed new ideas that increase Pastor's administrative capacity.	74.7	22.7	1.3	1.3	3.71	0.5 4	1 st
5	Engaging in further studies/training in pastoral ministry and professional courses assist in building capacity for administrative skills of pastors.	61.3	32.0	5.3	1.3	3.53	0.6 6	5 th
6	Organizing leaders and workers meetings/seminars contribute to capacity building.	66.2	28.4	1.4	4.1	3.57	0.7 2	4 th
7	Engaging in personal	48.6	47.3	2.7	1.4	3.43	0.6 2	6 th

8	development through selection of relevant literature improves capacity building. Capacity building entails sacrifices, patience, and endurance for some time.	69.3	24.0	5.3	3.67	0.6 0	2 nd
---	---	------	------	-----	------	----------	-----------------

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 2 shows the opinions of the respondents on the nature of capacity building among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Research Question 2: To what extent does the church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administrative skills?

Table 3a shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing administrative skill (planning) among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Table 3a: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Planning

S/ N	Statements on Planning	VO (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	R a n k
1	Preparing ahead for activities/ <u>programmes</u> to be done in the church.	68.7	25.3	4.7	1.3		4.61	0.64	1 st
2	Doing long-term, short-term, and immediate task planning.	34.9	45.6	15.4	4.0		4.11	0.81	3 rd
3	Readjusting plans periodically in the light of new information and changes in operating conditions.	26.4	33.8	31.1	8.1	0.7	3.77	0.96	5 th
4	Gathering information, identify and describe possible problems.	28.7	46.0	20.0	4.0	1.3	3.97	0.88	4 th
5	Considering possible options of solution to identified problems.	36.7	45.3	13.3	4.0	0.7	4.13	0.84	2 nd

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3b: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Organising

S/ N	Statements on Organizing	V (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Connecting members into mutually beneficial relationships, specifically those with a common task or purpose.	26.0	41.3	23.3	4.7	4.0	4.15	4.30	2 nd
2	Grouping related activities together and setting up a line of authority for operational effectiveness.	22.7	46.0	19.3	8.0	4.0	3.75	1.02	5 th
3	Arranging people within the church to get a particular task done.	42.7	39.3	12.0	4.7	1.3	4.17	0.91	1 st
4	Setting up certain rules for teamwork to enable people to work harmoniously together under all possible circumstances.	38.7	34.7	18.0	4.7	4.0	3.99	1.06	3 rd
5	Establishing platforms that will help meet the social needs of people doing the work of the Lord.	30.7	40.7	18.7	4.0	6.0	3.86	1.09	4 th

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3b shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing organizing as part of the administrative skills among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Table 3c: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Directing

S/N	Statements on Directing	VO (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Having a good grasp of what people are to do.	43.0	43.6	10.1	2.0	1.3	4.24	0.82	1 st
2	Indicating what others are to do.	32.7	42.7	22.0	1.3	1.3	4.04	0.85	5 th
3	Providing an agreed agenda of what people are to do.	38.7	42.7	12.0	5.3	1.3	4.12	0.91	3 rd
4	Taking time to explain the method to get the job done.	40.7	36.0	14.7	8.0	0.7	4.08	0.97	4 th
5	Directing subordinates to understand and contribute effectively and efficiently to the attainment of church goals.	48.7	34.0	10.7	5.3	1.3	4.23	0.94	2 nd

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3c shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing directing as part of the administrative skills among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Table 3d: The Extent of Practice Administration Skills – Controlling

S/N	Statements Controlling	VO (%)	O (%)	S (%)	R (%)	N (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Directing, guiding, restraining, and keeping people within the limit.	25.2	43.5	21.1	7.5	2.7	3.81	0.99	5 th
2	Measuring the progress of the planned programmes.	27.2	51.7	16.3	2.0	2.7	3.99	0.88	3 rd
3	Correcting deviations from standard practices.	31.5	42.3	14.8	8.1	3.4	3.91	1.04	4 th
4	Introducing the right ideas at the right time to achieve the goal of the church.	52.7	31.8	10.8	4.1	0.7	4.66	4.26	1 st
5	Displaying integrity to exercise necessary control.	51.0	32.9	11.4	3.4	1.3	4.29	0.90	2 nd

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 3d shows the opinions of the respondents on the extent of practicing controlling as part of the administrative skills among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Research Question 3: What are the factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Table 4: Factors Affecting Capacity Building for Administrative Skills Development among Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

S/N	Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Lack of incentives often discourages Pastors to	21.3	61.3	16.0	1.3	3.03	0.66	5 th

	build capacity.							
2	Inadequate funding often incapacitate pastors to build their capacity	42.7	49.3	5.3	2.7	3.32	0.70	2 nd
3	The environment where the pastor lives also affect the pastor's capacity building.	41.3	41.3	13.3	4.0	3.20	0.82	3 rd
4	Some churches have policies that hinder their pastors for further training until after some years.	39.2	51.4	9.5		3.84	4.77	1 st
5	Some pastors are badly influenced by their friends from building their capacity.	20.0	60.0	18.7	1.3	2.99	0.67	6 th
6	Nature of some pastors' homes	22.7	62.7	13.3	1.3	3.07	0.64	4 th

	sometimes debars them from building their capacity.							
7	The workload in some churches prevents some pastors from attending further training.	25.3	44.0	25.3	5.3	2.89	0.84	7 th

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 4 shows the opinions of the respondents on the factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

Research Question 4: What are the benefits of capacity building to administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference?

Table 5: Benefits of Capacity Building to Administrative Skills Development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference

S/N	Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	SD	Rank
1	Capacity building improves the overall performance of a pastor as a result of	64.7	30.0	4.7	0.7	3.61	0.65	1 st

2	administrative skills acquired Capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation, church ministries, and human resources development.	57.3	38.7	4.0		3.55	0.61	2 nd
3	Capacity building increases pastors' morale and motivation.	59.0	34.2	6.0	0.7	3.53	0.66	3 rd
4	Capacity building helps to prevent frustration and burn-out in ministry.	49.3	42.0	7.3	1.3	3.41	0.71	7 th
5	Capacity building causes the growth of the church ministries (expansion).	58.6	34.0	4.7	2.7	3.50	0.73	5 th
6	Capacity building moves a beneficiary	56.7	38.7	3.3	1.3	3.51	0.64	4 th

	from one level of competence to a higher one.							
7	Leaders involved in the regular capacity building become more relevant with developments and information for solving complex daily problems at workplace.	58.7	33.3	8.0		3.51	0.65	4 th
8	Those engaged in constant capacity building have more opportunities for promotion or occupying higher official positions.	55.7	38.3	4.0	2.0	3.48	0.68	6 th

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 5 shows the opinions of the respondents on the benefits of capacity building to administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference.

to share certain information, familiar with problems within or without, and create appropriate solutions to the identified problem, and in doing these, other would get some inspiration on how to lead.

Also, it is cleared from the findings that In-Service training received a low ranking (7th). This shows that Pastors from Oyo Baptist Conference has a poor attitude to in-service training. This implies that they are not used to in-service training as a way of developing their capacities and the capacities of their members. According to Osanwonyi (2016:83), in-service training enhances job performance, and the absence of it retards professional growth. Now, the implication of not having in-service training by Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference is that their ministerial job performance would have been hindered, and at the same time their professional growth retarded.

Furthermore, findings from research question one also indicates that many Pastors in Oyo Baptist Conference do not attend workshop as this was rated least among other nature of the capacity building. That means they do not believe so much that capacity building can be enhanced through attending workshops. The result of this finding is not in consonance with the submission of Ogbonaya (2011) and Okenjom et al. (2017), who assert that attending workshops serves as a device to upgrade professional efficiency. Therefore, attending workshops by the Pastor of Oyo Baptist Conference is critical as this would help then to improve them as far as pastoral ministry is concerned.

Research question two found out the extent to which Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference practice administrative skills. Regarding planning as one of the administrative skills, this study indicates that Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference usually prepared ahead for activities to be done in the church as this was ranked first. This finding agrees with the opinion of Ayandokun (2016:67), who states that “planning involves the preparation of things to be done and the method in which it would be achieved.” This suggests that these Pastors would have imagined things or activities to do and how others would be influenced to achieve the expected results. Again, on the issue of planning, the findings also reveal that Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference rarely readjust their plans

periodically in the light of new information and changes in operating conditions. This finding opposes the view of Tidwell (1985:204) that planning involves identifying and describing possible problems and at the same time finding solutions to them. That means since they hardly readjust their programmes or activities, they might not be able to proffer necessary solutions to the identified problem.

The result of organising as part of the administrative skills discloses that Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference engage in arranging people within the church to get a particular task done as this was rated first among other statements. This result is in agreement with the take of Ishola-Esan (2014:32) that “organising is a way of establishing effective interpersonal relationship that enables a particular organisation to work. That is, the arrangement of people to get the job done.” Becker (1964:102), Mincer (1974:34), and Barney (1991:105) postulate that people are assets to any organisation, and any investment to improve their capacities will generate a meaningful result. The implication of the statements of Ishola-Esan, Becker, Mincer, and Barney is that church members must be seen as assets God has deployed to the church to do the work of the church and they must be arranged based on certain factors to establish interpersonal relationship and to do a particular job or assignment given to them. The issue of interpersonal relationships is essential because if the relationship among them is not cordial, the expected job or duty will not be done.

Similarly, the result of organising also shows that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference are lagging in grouping related activities together and set up a line of authority for operational effectiveness. This finding is an excellent pointer to the fact that some of these pastors might be weak administratively because they rated themselves low when it comes to the grouping of activities or jobs to be performed by their members and on who reports to whom. That is, setting a line of authority. This result contradicts the position of Wedel (1966:33) who submits that organising involves grouping of related activities and setting up a line of authority. Therefore, for these pastors to become more effective in the usage of

organising skill, they need to know how to group activities and individuals that would champion those activities together.

Another finding that this study discovered is the extent of practicing directing. The results obtained indicate that the respondents (Pastors) have a good grasp of what people are to do. They also direct their subordinates to understand and contribute effectively and efficiently to the attainment of church goals. This finding supports the claim of Ogungbangbe (2002:121) who affirms that church leaders and administrators ought to know and communicate their followers and other members for effective performance of their duties.

Further discovery in this aspect of directing is also alarming in the sense that, the results point to the fact that these church pastors have good grasp of what people are to do, they even direct their subordinates to understand and contribute effectively and efficiently to the attainment of the church goal, but they do not indicate well what others are to do as rated least from the result. This is contrary to the belief of scholars like Tidwell (1985:210) who states that a good director is expected to indicate what others are to do in the group in a way that gets the job done. Since people remains the great assets of any organisation, therefore it is expected that what they are to do must be well communicated. This is what is usually called a job description in the modern-day business world. Telling church members what to do and how to do it will allow them to unleash their energies, resources, and their abilities toward the realisation of the missions of the church.

Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference also displayed controlling as part of administrative skills. This work indicates that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference introduce the right ideas at the right time to achieve the goal of the church. This finding agrees with the position of Ogungbangbe (2002:130) that when leaders introduce the right ideas at an appropriate time, it will lead to a certain measure of control. This suggests that people should not be administered by using force; rather the introduction of what to do at the right time will lead to a certain measure of control. Further discovery about controlling is the fact that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference display integrity to exercise necessary control.

Adetunji's (2010:70) opinion corroborates this discovery and claims that "Integrity is the quality of being honest and firm in one's moral principle." It is the quality of standing for what one knows is right.

The opinion of Tidwell (1986:216) that "one of the ways to uphold control is to maintain integrity" also supports this finding of display of integrity by the Pastor of Oyo Baptist Conference. People tend to follow a leader whose yes is yes and whose no is no. Lack of integrity will cause pastors to lose grip over their members, and once that happens, control is gone. Another finding is that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference measure the progress of the planned programmes. This finding goes along with the claim of Ogunbangbe (2002:131) who posits that "control is used to monitor the advancement of the programme and procedures in the plan. Through control system, deviations from the standard practice are detected." The implication is that control remains a powerful instrument in the hands of pastors who wish to check some deviations from standard practices so that the organisation's goals can be realised.

Research question three identified factors affecting capacity building for administrative skills development among church Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. This work reveals that some churches have policies that hinder their pastors for further training until after some years. The reason for this could be as a result of the experiences of some churches in the past whereby some pastors were given the opportunities for further studies, and after their training they opted for what seems to be "greener pasture" - "better church." This has really taught some churches lessons before they came up with the idea that for some years when a pastor resumes work, there will not be an opportunity for further study. But the era we are in now has gone beyond going into four-walled institutions before building capacity. There are a lot of online courses that could be done with reputable schools that will not cause any travelling.

Similarly, this work also shows that inadequate funding often incapacitates pastors to build their capacities. The take-home of some pastors incapacitates some pastors to engage in further studies that

might lead to building capacities that would help them to develop necessary administrative skills. In addition to this, this work also indicates that the environment where some pastors live also affects pastors' capacity building. Oyo Baptist Conference has almost fifty percent of their churches in the rural area. For instance, the association that this researcher belongs to has twenty-one (21) churches, and out of these, ten (10) are located in the villages where there is bad or no network at all. For this set of pastors, it might be a bit difficult to build their capacities especially through further studies, workshops, seminars and conferences. But they can also improve themselves through reading of related literature that can help to develop their capacities with regard to administrative skills. Books on leadership and Church Administration can assist.

Another critical finding of factors that affect capacity building for administrative skills development is the nature of some pastors' homes sometime debar them from building their capacities. This factor is equally real. The nature of some pastors' homes especially those who still have growing children who are still in dependent age brackets, might find it difficult to excuse themselves from homes for further study owing to the fact that people look up to pastors' homes to be an ideal home. So, the fear of who will assist in the upbringing of the children grip many pastors and prevent them from further studies.

Research question four investigated what benefits capacity building has on administrative skills development among church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference. It was discovered that capacity building improves the overall performance of a pastor as a result of administrative skills acquired. This finding is in line with the finding of Chatira and Mwenje (2018:111), who submit that capacity building improves the effectiveness of pastors and making them more relevant in the ministry. Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7) also agree with the same view and presents that capacity building improves the overall productivity of workers in any organisation. In the findings of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7), 40.94% of the respondents indicated strongly agreed (SA) and 37.80% indicated agreed (A) compared with 64.7% (SA) and 30% (A) obtained in this

result. Okenjom et al. (2017:479) also obtained 77% (SA) and 22 (A) on the fact that capacity building improves the overall performance of the workers in any established organisation. The implication of this discovery is that pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference must give attention to various activities that will lead to capacity building because this result indicates that it will improve their performance as a result of administrative skills acquired. It is also safe to infer that building capacity would bring about the development of administrative skills.

In the same vein, this work reveals that capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation, church ministries, and human resources development. This finding agrees with the argument of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6-7) that capacity building creates an absolute commitment to innovation and system commitment. Their result points out that their respondents indicate 40.50% (SA) and 37.80% (A) respectively and this work got 57.30% (SA) and 38.7% (A) correspondingly. It is certain that the world we live in today is not stable, is ever dynamic. This calls for pastors involving in ministries to give heed to capacity building so that various innovations that will move the church forward can be birthed. Not only this but also leading to the development of other human resources in the church because people remain the great asset of any organisation, and it is not possible to give what people do not have. Hence, building capacity is indispensable.

Furthermore, this work reveals that capacity building increases pastors' morale and motivation. The position of Ojokuku and Adejare (2014:6) supports this finding and argues that capacity building through training and attending workshops will increase staff morale and motivation. Also, this result shows that capacity building has the tendency to permit a beneficiary to move from one level of competence to a higher one.

This finding also agrees with the stance of Biswas (1996:401), who argues that capacity building moves competent individuals from one level of proficiency to a higher level. This statement of Biswas finds expression in Matthew chapter twenty-five in the parable of talent where the master gives commendation to those two servants that traded with five and two talents to gained five and two more respectively. This

implies that those two servants move from one level of proficiency to a higher one. This is also expected of pastors who desired to satisfy the master.

Similarly, this work also reveals that leaders who involve in the regular capacity building become more relevant with developments and information for solving a complex daily problem at work. This finding aligns with the assertion of Graffin (2015:5) and Woodruff (2004) who declare that leaders who engage in capacity building become more relevant within the organisation. Pastors need to strive to become more relevant in ministry. This is very crucial. The master (Jesus) wants that. This could be inferred from Jesus' statement in Matthew 4:19, that says "Come, follow me, and I will make you fishers of men." This statement of Jesus is a statement to make his followers relevant to his ministry here on earth. Therefore, it is safe to make this statement that pastors who engage in capacity building stand to become more relevant in the ministry and the kingdom business at large.

Conclusion

This research acknowledged that capacity building by church pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference with respect to administrative skills development occurred majorly through attending professional conferences like ministers' conference, though few of them have a poor attitude to in-service training and workshops as other means of building their capacities. Also, it is established that the extent of practicing administrative skills by Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference is high. Furthermore, the findings have established the fact that capacity building with respect to administrative skills development improves the overall performance of a pastor and church policies have been discovered to be the prominent factors, among others that affect capacity building. On the contribution to knowledge by the outcomes of this study, the following facts are deduced. There exists a relationship between capacity building and administrative skills development. Capacity building through attendance of professional conferences, in-service training, and workshops would lead to the development of

administrative skills which would in turn bring about improvement in the overall performance of a pastor and, enhance the quality of services provided by the church. As much as these discoveries are real, capacity building calls for patience, endurance, and sacrifices from the aspect of pastors

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should explore every opportunity that would lead to the building of their capacities. They should not limit themselves to ministers' conference programme alone;
2. Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should learn more about administrative skills through the reading of relevant literature so that the way they administer the church would be improved;
3. Churches of Oyo Baptist Conference should create platforms and encourage their pastors to engage in capacity building rather than using policies that would not allow them to build their capacities; and
4. Pastors of Oyo Baptist Conference should also explore internet facility to shuffle the net and discover some on-line courses that may be free, and at the same time that would lead to the building of their capacities.

References

- Adetunji, O. G. (2010). *Leadership in Action: A Sourcebook in Church Administration for Students and Ministers*. Ibadan: Baptist Press Limited.
- Andrews, B., and Roller, R. (2011). *Pastoral Preparation for Ministry Management and Leadership*. Available Online: <http://studylib.net/doc/5231671/pastoral-preparation-for-ministry-management-and-leadership>,
- Akintola, S. O. (2020). *New Testament Theology: An African Perspective*. Ibadan: Baptist Press.

- Ayandokun, E. O. (2016). *A Manual on Educational Administration in the Church: Growing the Church through Effective Teaching Ministry Using all Church's Educational Ministry*. Lagos: Gloryline Christian Publication.
- Barney, J. (1991). "Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage." *Journal of Management*, Vol. 17 (1), 99-120.
- Becker, G. S. (1964). *A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to Education*. New York: Colombia University Press.
- Biswas, A. K. (1996). "Capacity Building for Water Management: Some Personal Thoughts." *Water Resources Development*, Vol. 12(4), 399-405.
- Chatira, F., and Mwanje, J. (2018). "The Development of Management Skills for Effective Church Management in Pastoral Preparation Programmes in Zimbabwe." *Africa Journal of Business Management*, Vol. 12(5), 103-120.
- Claussen, C. (2011). *Capacity Building for Organizational Effectiveness*. Available Online: <https://www.calgaryumtedway.org>,
- Fatiloru, O. (2018). "Influence of Church Administration to the Pastoral Functions of Pastor in Churches of Ogbomoso Baptist Conference." Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, Submitted to Faculty of Education, The Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso.
- Graffin, R. W. (2015). *Management*. USA: Cengage Learning South-western.
- Imhabekai, C. (1998). *Programme Development and Programme Management in Adult and Non-formal Education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Anfitop Books Nigeria Ltd.
- Ishola-Esan, H. (2014). "The Use of Basic Skills of Administration for Church Growth." *Asia-Africa Journal of Mission and Ministry*, Vol.13 (35), 31-51.
- Khan, A. (2014). "Education Role in Capacity Building." *International Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 05-11.
- Mincer, J. (1995). "Schooling, Experience, and Earnings." In McLean, J.E. (Ed.). *Improving Education through Active Research: A Guide for Administrators and Teachers*. Thousand Oaks: Corwin Press Inc.
- Murphey, C, and Chand, S. (1996). *Futuring: Leading your Church into Tomorrow*. Wheaton: Tyndale House Publishers.
- Nakpodia, E. D. (2011). "Teacher Factors in the Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Junior Secondary Schools in the South

- Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria.” *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research*, Vol.3 (10), 286-293.
- Noort, M. (2012). Building Capacity Strategy. Available Online: webapps.itc.utwente.nl/librerywww/paper_2012/general/noort_capacity.pdf,
- Nworgu, B. G. (2006). *Educational Research: Basic Issues and Methodology*. Second and Enlarge Edition. Ibadan: Wisdom Publishers Ltd.
- Odu, B. K., Ayodele, C. J., and Adebayo, J. O. (2014). “Empowering the Youth for Sustainable National Development through Vocational Education in Southwest Nigeria.” *International Journal of Research and Development*, Vol. 3 (1), 001-005.
- Ogbonaya, C. (2011). “Evaluation and Supervision of Instructions in Nigeria School.” In E. A. Beson and Nwokocha, L. K. (Eds) *Educational Administration and Management in Nigeria: The Salient Issues*. Owerri: Soletech Press.
- Ogungbangbe, J. A. (2002). *Church Administration: A Practical Approach*. Lagos: CSS Limited.
- Ojokuku, R. M., and Adejare, T. A. (2014). “The Impact of Capacity Building Development on Staff Performance in Selected Organizations in Nigeria.” *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, Vol. 11(5), 1-9.
- Okenjom, G. P., Laura A., Ikurite, N., and Ihekoronye, J. I. (2017). “Capacity Building Programme Needs for School Administrators in Secondary School in Cross River State, Nigeria.” *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol. 2 (7), 478-482.
- Osanwonyi, E. F. (2016). “In-Service Education of Teachers: Overview, Problems and the Way Forward.” *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol. 7(26), 83-87.
- Savitskaya, I. S. (2015). “Refresher Courses for School Teachers of English at Tomsk State University.” *Procedia-Social and Behaviour Science*, No.200, 366-371.
- Tidwell, C. A. (1985). *Church Administration Effective Leadership for Ministry*. USA: Broadman Press.
- What is Conference? Available Online:, <https://evenues.com/event-planning-guide/what-is-a-conference>,
- Woodruff, T. R. (2004). Executive Pastor’s Perception of Leadership and Management Competencies needed for Local Church Administration.

Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication

(ISSN 3043-4416)

*The Journal of the Department of Religious and Intercultural
Studies, Faculty of Arts, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria*

Volume 2, Number 1, August 2024

Ph.D. Thesis. The Southern Baptist Theological Seminary. Available
Online: [https://
www.xpastor.org/wpcontent/uploads/2012/12/woodruff_competencie
s_needed.pdf](https://www.xpastor.org/wpcontent/uploads/2012/12/woodruff_competencie
s_needed.pdf),

Yamoah, E. E. (2014). "The Link between Human Resource Capacity Building
and Job Performance." *International Journal of Human Resource
Studies*, Vol. 4 (3), 139-146.